

Sensory Aesthetics: Social Sciences can Inform Aesthetics

Moin Rahman* Ira Jhangiani*

*Motorola
Plantation, FL.
moin.rahman@motorola.com
ira.jhangiani@gmail.com

Abstract: Any modern, functional artifact – the car, cellphone, camera, etc. – can be viewed as a microcomputer-driven machine with its human-machine interface embodied in multiple mediums. They not only have to deliver a function(s) but should also fulfill the affective and aesthetic needs of the user through the many mediums (physical, virtual, aural, etc.) in which they are manifested. A construct called ‘sensory aesthetics’ has been conceived to investigate the processing of aesthetic information contained in such a functional artifact by its users. At an operational level, it postulates that the aesthetic information is filtered through a set of six concatenated, overlapping filters (deep structures, culture, ecology, behaviors, affordance and epoch). The filtering approach is rooted in the social and psychological sciences due to the fact that culture, context and cognitions are the primary drivers through which a group’s – and by extension an individual’s – aesthetic sense and needs are shaped. In the practice standpoint, information gleaned through the sensory aesthetics approach can be used to make informed decisions and shape the aesthetics of a product and its interface for a given context and users. Finally, the sensory aesthetics approach demonstrates that social science and art can partner in constructive ways in the product design process.

Keywords: *Sensory aesthetics, art, industrial design, product & interface design, culture, emotion, cognition.*

1. Introduction

Art and science – and, by extension, artists and scientists – are traditionally viewed as tenuously connected human endeavors. That artists purportedly thrive in creativity that is fueled by chaos whereas scientists supposedly survive on empirical rigor and worship analytical thought. As the scientific revolution blossomed, the fissure between the sciences and art deepened. It was lamented that calculation and measurement displaced the cultivation and passion engendered by the arts [1].

One may argue that the notions of artistic and scientific creativity are convenient social constructions that channel the emotional and rational pursuits of humanity. For instance, it is an accepted fact that architecture informs the aesthetics of a building whereas engineering provides its structural solutions. However, this rigid bifurcation is being blurred of late by new and novel emerging architectural practices such as *Informal* [2]. For example, one of the motifs of the *Informal* school is to expose and accentuate how the [load-bearing] structure counters and routes the forces of gravity – and, in the process, engenders an aesthetic appreciation around the structure itself in the mind of the perceiver.

1.1 Machine as Art

The “new art” of “industrial design” came as a response to the rise of machine-made mass products [3] in order

to increase their appeal by going beyond the essential requirements such as functionality and usability. In other words, a machine or tool had to artistically express itself through its character and composition to fulfill the emotional needs of the user. Furthermore, from the semiotic point of view, it had to not only denote function but also had to connote symbolic value [4] such as class, status, wealth, austerity, power, etc. The value proposition in the manufacturer's standpoint was straightforward: to make the product saleable it had to be made palatable to the human senses. In recent years this has been studied under the rubric of the 'power of positive affect' – the perception that “attractive things work better” and the role of “pleasure” in human-product interaction [5, 6].

1.2 Humans and their Arts

Humans are said to have an innate predisposition and proclivity to create and consume art. Ethologists point out that art, as a trait has been selected by evolution, as it provides “enabling mechanisms for the performance of selectively valuable behaviors such as appropriating the material needs of life” (food, tools, shelter, etc.) [7]. For instance, it is conjectured that prehistoric man – in a dangerous, unknown, unsure and unpredictable world – made sure that his technology (spear, pottery, etc.) worked by deliberately reinforcing it with emotionally satisfying special [artistic] elaborations and shaping. Cultural anthropologists have pointed out that art was integral to ritual whose purpose was to inculcate group identity, cooperation, cohesiveness and cooperation [7]. Furthermore, anthropologists have also conjectured that a group by imposing its culture on nature, sought to control nature.

1.3 Industrialized Art

In earlier times, the consumer was his own designer and artist (designer-artist-consumer); and as civilization advanced consumers and designers evolved separate identities due to the specialization of the latter, but were still situated at close proximity that enabled the former to directly influence the style, form and functional aspects of the product. However, these earlier models have been supplanted with the industrialization of technology, chiefly characterized by mass production. This has not only divorced designers and end-users but has further increased the distance between them in terms of country, culture, climate, etc. This paper is positioned to close this distance insofar by enabling the designers glean the aesthetic needs (implicit and explicit) of their target audience by taking a systematic approach through the realm of the social sciences.

2. Reconnections

A literature review has shown no formal theory, practice or tradition exists, from the social sciences standpoint, to systematically inform the aesthetics of a product. As a first step, certain basic concepts on aesthetics and aesthetic theory will be discussed in the next few sections.

2.1 Aesthetics

The ancient Greeks used the term “aesthetic” to refer to sensation and feelings – good or bad, beautiful or ugly [8]. However, modern usage has somewhat corrupted the original connotation and now it is used as a synonym for something that is perceived as “beautiful.” The objective here is to use the word aesthetic in its original sense.

2.2 Sensory Aesthetics

Many artifacts stimulate one or more senses – tactile, olfactory, auditory and visual – as part of their function

(e.g., ring tone on a cellphone) or do it as an incidental byproduct of their function (e.g., the crack of a rifle shot; a sports car's engine sound and equilibrioception [sense of linear acceleration]). These unimodal or multimodal stimulations (visual and non-visual) are crucial because it has been argued that the body with its total sensing apparatus assesses the environmental conditions in multiple modalities on a cathectic basis; that is, intuitive, emotional, uninformed judgment, feel good or feel bad, adumbration, making benefit or loss assessments, adjusting and readjusting [9]. In other words, these “good and the bad” multimodal sensory experiences – are the foundations for “aesthetics,” as originally conceived by the ancient Greeks. This paper reclaims the original sense of the word by placing it in a modern and social science context. To facilitate this distinction and provide a modern connotation, with its roots in social science, the term “*Sensory Aesthetics*” has been coined. Sensory aesthetics can be defined as a first order sensory-driven orientation response that is automatic, fast, instinctive, non-conscious, and effortless to the good and the bad aspects of the stimuli resulting in an instant and implicit conclusion on its valence. In the sensory standpoint, it is analogous to the concept of *direct perception* [10], in the physical environment, where an organism gleans meaning inherent in its environment without any explicit mental calculation. In the social domain (human-human interaction), its akin to ‘thin slicing’ [11] – i.e., reliably gleaning information through “instantaneous impressions” about a person’s identity, disposition and intent, with a brief exposure.

Aesthetics of a product can be reliably sensed through thin slicing and it neither requires inferential reasoning nor is it necessary that it be mediated by language. The concept of sensory aesthetics can be best appreciated in the words of Le Corbusier [12] who made his observations concerning the empathetic ideals of architecture: “...the disposition of elements in a building should be such a way that the sight of them affects us immediately by their delicacy or their brutality, their riot or their serenity, their indifference or their interest.” At a subjective level, it can be said that the sensory aesthetic experience engenders an “esthetic emotion” [13], which is said to arise before any experience or knowledge of the object can be accumulated.

In a human information processing standpoint, the sensory aesthetic experience should be viewed as a gradually changing continuum, with the bulk of the processing occurring at the visceral level (which is automatic, fast, parallel and affectively-centered) and diminishing as one ascends to the higher cortical centers (where slow, deliberate, serial and rational cognition occurs) of the brain. The opposite of *sensory aesthetic* is the *cogitated aesthetic* where the affective reaction of a product’s aesthetics is generated through deliberate analysis (intellectualization and rationalization). An example of the cogitated aesthetic would be the manner in which an user marvels and reflects upon the connecinity, symmetry, craftsmanship or finish of a product’s form factor (e.g., sports car). Don Norman’s three-level processing model [5] to visually describe and contrast the sensory and cogitated aesthetics, respectively (Figure 1).

In design theory, Norman’s design framework has been interpreted as having three rigid levels [14], which, in turn, evoke three very different cognitive reactions: (1) aesthetic impression (visceral level cognition: attractive/unattractive); (2) semantic interpretation (behavioral level cognition: functional/use); and (3) symbolic association (reflective level cognition: personal/social significance). However, the definition of sensory aesthetic – informed by the fact that affect precedes cognition, i.e., “preferences need no inferences” [15] – does

not adhere to the rigid, three level model. Because the user can non-consciously sense the affective component present at all three levels (visceral, behavioral and reflective) at once, to varying [diminishing] degrees without requiring deliberate cognition. For example, a certain watch can be perceived as having ‘high’ status merely on first impressions because it simply ‘feels’ elegant and sophisticated. This precludes any formal cognition such as deliberate analysis of material, finish or [discretionary] branding information [8].

Figure 1. Sensory vs. Cogitated Aesthetic: viewed under the rubric of Don Norman’s [5] three-level [user] processing of design.

3. Discovering the Sensory Aesthetic

The idea of universal design – as applied to form (not to be confused with design for people with disabilities) – has received its fair share of criticism [16]. This is because universal design seeks a language of product form compatible with any technology, for any culture at any time. The aesthetic here is valorized and commoditized because of its enforced uniformity, which neither takes into account individual tastes nor cultural norms of a people. Furthermore, the intense competition prevailing in the marketplace, results in asymmetric attention [rightfully so] being paid to non-aesthetic attributes of a product, such as functionality, features, usability, price, etc., at the cost of aesthetics.

In a fast paced industrial setting, there is insufficient time to pay enough thought to discovering the ideal aesthetic for a product; universal design often times becomes the recourse. Moreover, a formal process – using either the social or psychological sciences – is not readily available to quickly and efficiently inform the development of the aesthetic of a product besides a few exceptions, with limited scope (e.g., Kansei [17]).

The rest of the paper describes a systematic process – informed by the social and psychological sciences – that can be used to discover the elements, which are responsible in the manifestation of the sensory aesthetic.

4. Aesthetic fitness

The concept of aesthetics in product design can be studied through at least two avenues:

- 1) The ‘artistic universals’ approach that are prerequisites to evoke a positive valence in the minds of the perceivers regardless of their culture, ecology, etc. This approach usually involves determining

attributes that are required to evoke a positive valence in terms of mass, surface and plan [13], form, proportion, arrangement, connecivity, novelty, etc. [8], Gestalt psychology [11], and neuroaesthetics [18].

- 2) The fitness of the aesthetic for a specific set of users in terms of their culture, context and purpose (high level goals) – by viewing them as particularized instances or localizations.

This paper will utilize the second avenue – i.e., explore the role of cultural, social, contextual, temporal factors, among others – in shaping a group’s aesthetic appetite and how it could inform the design of a product. Design literature is replete with a variety of aesthetic frameworks that are centered on integration (style, performance, utility and story) [23], information-processing [8], interaction [24], among others. But these frameworks crucially fall short in two areas:

- 1) They emphasize *additive* integration, *non-affective* information processing, or *affect* arising out of interaction (pragmatic aesthetics). Furthermore, they do not consider the interaction among different factors that underpin aesthetics, or the possibility of them acting as filters in the manifestation of an individual’s or group’s perception of aesthetics.
- 2) They do not explain in sufficient detail as to how the various factors (cognitive to social) may operate in the perception of aesthetics, thus making it difficult to operationalize them in design research and practice.

5. Six Filters

Aesthetics of a product neither emerges *ex nihilo* nor does it exist in the absence of a human perceiver. The perceiver filters the [sensory] aesthetics of a product through his culture, knowledge, experiences, historical epoch – including the repertoire of proximal behaviors he expects to perform with the product to fulfill an ultimate need. These six filters were identified based on theoretical and empirical knowledge available in the social sciences, particularly in the realms of how individual and group cognitions and emotions emerge and are shaped by their social and physical ecosystems, including their past histories and purported future trajectories.

Deep Structures: Products exist to fulfill certain needs (e.g., transportation, communication, security, etc.) and to satiate emotional needs (e.g., display status, intrinsic pleasure, etc.). The ‘needs’ are really the tip of the iceberg as they reside on deeply-rooted desires (e.g., Maslow’s hierarchy of needs) that are driven by intrinsic (derived from play, feelings of belonging, balance and coherence) and extrinsic motivations (anticipation of goal accomplishment). The ability\inability of a product to convey its fitness to fulfill the deep structures will influence if the aesthetics is either perceived positively or negatively. For example, a consumer who puts safety as a top issue when shopping for an automobile will accord a higher aesthetic valence to a model whose mass, form, plan, proportion, among other elements, aesthetically conveys attributes such as strength, sturdiness and protection.

Ecology: A product has to be harmonious in the ecology in which it is used. The ecology is shaped by the geographical, physical, demographic, organizational and semiotic setting. If a product’s aesthetic is out of place with its ecology it will be perceived negatively. For example, a colorful, snazzy, highly dynamic interface commonly seen on gaming devices for teenagers may not be appropriate as a theme on a human-machine interface used on a commercial aircraft.

Behaviors: The rituals and rhythms of living, working and playing are governed by master routines known as fundamental or prosematic [19] behaviors, which are governed by the ‘primitive’ emotional centers in the brain.

As these behaviors are adaptive (selected by evolution) they are of high value to an organism. If a product's look and feel is perceived as supportive, or amplifying the prosematic behavior(s) governing a particular activity, it will be much preferred over another product that may lack these qualities.

Culture: The culture governing a human collective (e.g., nationality, firefighters, urban teens, etc.) shapes their beliefs, preferences and predispositions. A product's aesthetic should be harmonious with a group's culture to be accepted and appreciated. For instance, a 'contractor-grade' power tool that has too much of aesthetic detail (relief, lines and colors), may not win the approval of a group of workers belonging to the construction industry.

Affordances: The intuitive grasp or potential for action should be palpable in a product. The information concerning the purpose and operation of product should be presented in a lucid, intuitive and inviting manner because the resulting affordance has the potential to enhance the aesthetic appeal of the product. For example, if a very beautiful looking DVD player does not immediately convey operational details (how to load a disc and play) through its interface because it provides either hidden or false affordance [20], then, its aesthetic appeal will be diminished.

Epoch: The epoch is the 'zeitgeist' [8] of an age. It is the 'spirit of the times,' which is manifested due to political or social revolutions or evolutions, popular sentiments and technological breakthroughs. It may also be shaped by trend setters, taste makers, reviewers, social commentators and culture critics present in a society. A product's aesthetics needs to be synchronous with its epoch if it has to appeal to its audience. For example, the first modern airliner, the Douglas DC-3, was the most influential icon of the 1930s. The airplane's aerodynamic form influenced the design of other products such as cars, locomotives – and even radios and refrigerators – as they sported smooth, curving and "streamlined" surfaces [8].

To reiterate the earlier point of sensory aesthetics, its argued that a consumer will be able to thin slice the aesthetic information of a product through these six filters, and instantly conclude – based on the valence, the aesthetic emotion it engenders – whether it is boring, exciting, beautiful or ugly. These six, lens-like filters can be considered as a concatenated set, with some overlaps, that affectively color the perception of a product's aesthetics, when resolved (brought into focus) in the mind of the perceiver (Figure 2).

It is plausible that a product and the setting or context in which its sensory aesthetic is perceived may alter the order, size and influence of these filters. For instance, in the case of a modern artifact such as a cellphone, *affordance* may move-up the hierarchy of filters – as there is an intrinsic psychological need to immediately perceive on how to use it and actually use/interact with it. Whereas, say, in the case of apparel *culture* and *epoch* will probably trump other filters in order and importance when a subject perceives the sensory aesthetic.

Figure 2. Perceiving the sensory aesthetic through six filters

5.1 A Deeper Look at Select Filters

Given the space constraints, only three of the six filters – ecology, culture and behavior – will be discussed in greater detail. (The law enforcement domain has been selected for illustration purposes.)

5.1.1 Ecology

A product has to live and thrive in the ecology that is native to its users. The elements of ecology in the context of product design are presented in the Table below.

Table 1. Elements of ecology and corresponding features

Elements of Ecology	Features (examples)
Geographical\Physical	terrain, climate, altitude, etc.
Demographic	socioeconomic strata, age group, gender, etc.
Operational modes	mobile vs. fixed; night vs. day; personal vs. work
Organizational codes	commercial vs. consumer; mission critical vs. non critical.
Interactions	slow vs. fast; economical vs. deliberative;
Semiotics	Symbology: colors, jargon, sounds, form-styling, etc.

Next the implications of ecology in the context of performing law enforcement for a high altitude railway system (railway link connecting Golmud, China to Lhasa, Tibet) are discussed. In Table 2, two ecological elements have been selected and expanded for illustration purposes. And Figure 3 provides a visual glimpse of the geographical\physical ecological elements.

Table 2. Elements of ecology and their aesthetic implications

Elements of Ecology	Features (examples)	Aesthetic Implications
Geographical Physical	Snowcapped mountains, high altitude (16,000 ft.), low oxygen (30% - 40% of sea level), cold, permafrost	Physically demanding, cognitive impoverishment (low oxygen), physiologically taxing, dangerous, high risk, scenic and breathtakingly beautiful
Semiotics	Tibetan's love for color and resplendence vs. the official Chinese [communist] aesthetic that is stark, dour and plain.	Conflicting aesthetics (Tibetan vs. Communist).

Figure 3 Perceiving the Police radio sensory aesthetic through six filters: a rugged look that conveys operability in extreme conditions

Table 2 and Figure 3 present the physical and semiotic aspects of the sensory aesthetics applicable to a police radio for the particular ecology under discussion, it is logical to conclude that the sensory aesthetic should embody a rugged and tough look, which unequivocally conveys that the radio can operate at low temperatures and withstand extreme weather elements (sleet, snow, rain, etc.).

These sensory aesthetic qualities when designed into the product will enhance appeal and make it more convincing. In other words, if a product has a sensory aesthetic incongruent to its ecology, and even if it meets performance specifications, the product may be perceived as unfit for the ecology in which it has to operate.

Furthermore, in this case, from a semiotic standpoint the product has to also resolve the conflicting aesthetics of the two ethnicities (Tibetan and Chinese) it tries to bridge. Furthermore, it needs to have an imprimatur that conveys officialdom, government and authority.

5.1.2 Culture

The social psychologist, Geert Hofstede, using the metaphor of computer software, succinctly defined culture as the “collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another”[21]. Hofstede identified three elements (symbols, values and rituals) and five independent dimensions of culture (power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individualism vs. collectivism, masculinity vs. femininity and long-term vs. short-term orientation). A social group’s aesthetic expectations are underpinned by its culture [elements and dimensions]. The cultural-aesthetic axis of a certain group is modulated based on where it lies (high\low) on the dimensions of culture [6] as shown in Table 3. Due to space constraints, just one element (*symbols*) and one power dimension (*masculinity vs. femininity*) of culture in the law enforcement context have been chosen for illustration.

Symbols are words, meanings, gestures and objects that carry often complex meanings recognized within that culture. Symbols are used to acquire and transmit patterned ways of thinking, feeling and reacting by a social group with the intent of providing group identity and herald its achievements. Law enforcement, as a culture, is rich with symbols that are used to send both explicit and implicit messages to within and without. This symbology can be observed from the uniforms (Figure 4), artifacts (ornamental and\or functional), styling of vehicles, communication jargon, etc. In this regard, symbology does share some common traits with semiotics discussed in the preceding section. Institutions, such as police departments, strive to create a shared framework of mental models amongst its members. Sociologists consider this shared mental model as an ‘ideology’ [of an

institution] that helps its members to interpret the environment and develop prescriptions on how the environment should be structured. The uniform, as a symbol, is thus used not only to distinguish the police officers from the rest of society (in-group vs. out-group), but also to help them develop a shared mental model so that they can function as a cohesive unit.

Table 3. Cultural-aesthetic axis: How the dimensions of culture (high/low) modulate a group’s aesthetic preferences [6].

Cultural Dimension	High	Low
Power distance (degree to which the unequal distribution of power is expected and accepted.)	High status	Youthfulness
Individuality (being self sufficient as opposed to being well integrated in the group’s social fabric.)	Expressiveness	Familiarity
Toughness – a.k.a., masculinity/femininity (tough vs. tender qualities.)	Performance	Artistry
Uncertainty avoidance (extent to which people feel threatened by ambiguity.)	Reliability	Novelty
Long-term orientation (extent to which people are future oriented.)	Timelessness	Fashionableness

Figure 4. A sample of police symbology (uniforms, artifacts, etc. from around the world (A) Tibet; (B) India; (C) Philippines (D) Iran; (E) Delaware, USA.

The sensory aesthetic of a law enforcement product should be pregnant with symbolism native to its ecology. Some select examples of how this could be accomplished are listed below.

- a. The sensory aesthetic should be in harmony with the symbology (Figure 4) – color, styling, etc. – used by a particular police department
- b. The sensory aesthetic of a police radio should express itself as a reliable connectivity tool with the rest of the force; and it should express to the citizens that additional help could be summoned at a moment’s notice.

The *masculinity vs. femininity* power dimension refers to the distribution of emotional roles between the genders in that it contrasts tough masculine against tender feminine qualities. The masculinity-femininity dimension should be seen as a social construct that transcends gender because of the fact that social groups tend to perceive masculinity/femininity even in inanimate objects. Although law enforcement is stereotyped as hyper masculine, it may not be the case with every law enforcement department. For instance, design research and industrial design done by Motorola’s Design & Integration department [25] has revealed an interesting contrast between

the London metro and the Korean police departments. Based on the history, political and cultural systems prevailing in each one of their countries, the former prefer to portray themselves as a friendlier, softer, caring and not-so-masculine group to the citizenry for the most part – i.e., unless they are threatened. The latter [Korea] show a preference to portray themselves as tough, assertive and very masculine. These two very different mindsets were then articulated in the sensory aesthetic [form factor] of the radios – same radio with different form factors -- designed for them. This was verified in the form factor testing phase and the final preferences are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Sensory aesthetic based on an organization’s cultural mindset.

As indicated above, determining a group’s cultural dimensions can provide insights on the kind of sensory aesthetics that might be desirable and acceptable.

5.1.3. Behavior

One of the major activities of law enforcement is to deter crime through “presence patrols.” In a prosematic behaviors (described earlier) standpoint, because it concerns territorial protection and defense, it involves the execution of what are known as “signature displays” and “challenge displays” [19]. The former are a form of asserting power visually and verbally, and the latter may involve dynamic posturing.

Figure 6. Signature & challenge displays of law enforcement officers

As seen in the figure above, the [organic form] of the signature display consists of a sufficiently tensed musculature (e.g., chest-up) resulting in assertive posture and vigilant facial expression. It is also expressed through its non-organic forms such as a sharp & snappy uniform (contrast this with the civilians in the background) and law-enforcement related equipment (on the belt), cap/beret, and insignia. Challenge display is expressed through the gait and authoritative pacing, display and swinging of the baton, sound of shoes hitting the pavement, etc.

The sensory aesthetic of a law enforcement product should bolster the behaviors intrinsic to it. This will require the product to display through its form, sounds, etc., character attributes such as “bold,” “assertive,” and “strong”; and compositional attributes such as “dependable,” “trustworthy” and “incorruptible.” Hence, a law enforcement product (e.g., radio) has an exogenous dimension in that it needs to convey through its sensory aesthetic – particularly form and finish – to the community at large that the officer is equipped with tools that are dependable and high quality.

6. Closing thoughts

The sensory aesthetic approach lays out a systematic process to uncover the aesthetic preferences of a specific target audience. As discussed earlier, it filters out the [desired-ideal] aesthetic by trying to understand the consumers’ deep structures, ecology, culture, affordance needs and epoch in a particular product-user interaction context. Obviously, what is presented in this paper is not an exhaustive and comprehensive approach to inform the development of a product’s aesthetic. But it provides a filtering approach and lays out a pathway to get to the [aesthetic] destination in an informed manner. Last but not least, the execution and the artistic ingenuity of the designer is still a vital factor in translating the information gleaned through the six filters into appropriate aesthetic expressions. Put another way, a good musical score or recipe can only succeed in the interpretations of a skilled string quartet or hands of a chef.

8. Acknowledgements

The authors thank Mark Palmer (Director, Human Factors, Motorola) for giving us the scientific license to explore the nexus between the arts and the sciences in the context of product design. Shantel Biangel, for the ‘six filters’ graphic that helped us visually articulate the sensory aesthetic framework. Ganesh Balakrishnan for assisting us with the literature review, particularly at the interaction of aesthetics, affordance and psychology.

9. References

- [1] Snow, C.P (1993). *The Two Cultures*. Cambridge University Press. New York, NY, USA.
- [2] Balmond, C. and Smith, J. (2002). *Informal*. Prestel, New York, NY. USA.
- [3] Cheney, S. and Cheney, M. (1936). *Art and the Machine: An Account of Industrial Design in 20th Century America*. McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- [4] Chandler, D. (2007). *Semiotics: The Basics* (2nd ed.). Routledge, New York, NY, USA.
- [5] Norman, D. A. (2004). *Emotional design: Why we Love (or Hate) Everyday Things*. Basic Books, New York, NY, USA.
- [6] Jordan, P.W. (2000). *Designing Pleasurable Products*. Taylor & Francis, Philadelphia, PA, USA.
- [7] Dissanayake, E. (1992). *Homo Aestheticus: Where Art Comes From and Why*. The Free Press, New York, NY, USA.
- [8] Coates, D. (2003). *Watches Tell More Than Time: Product Design, Information, and the Quest for Elegance*. McGraw-Hill, New York, NY, USA.

- [9] Winkler (2002) Design Language: Confluence of Behavioral, Social, and Cultural Factors. In J. Frascara (Ed.). *Design and the Social Sciences: Making Connections*. Taylor and Francis, New York, NY, USA.
- [10] Gibson, J. (1966). *The Senses Considered as Perceptual Systems*. Houghton Mifflin Company, Boston, MA, USA.
- [11] Ambady, N., Bernieri, F.J. and Richeson, J.A. (2000). Toward a Histology of Social Behavior: Judgmental Accuracy from Thin Slices of the Behavioral Stream. In M.F. Zanna (Ed.). *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 32, 201-271, Academic Press, New York, NY, USA.
- [12] Corbusier, Le. (1986). *Towards a New Architecture*. Dover Publications, New York, NY, USA, 1986.
- [13] Lewalski, Z.M. (1988). *Product Esthetics: An Interpretation for Designers*. Design & Development Engineering Press, Carson City, NV, USA.
- [14] Crilly, N. Moultrie, J., & Clarkson, P.J. (2004). Seeing things: consumer response to the visual domain in product design. *Design Studies*, 25, 547-577.
- [15] Zajonc, R. B. (1980). Feeling and thinking: Preferences need no inferences. *American Psychologist*, 35, 151-175.
- [16] McCoy, M. (1990). The post industrial designer: Interpreter of technology. In *Proc. Product Semantics 1989 Conference*, Publications of the Univeristy of Industrial Arts, Helsinki, Finland.
- [17] Nagamachi, M. (2002). Kansei engineering as a powerful consumer-oriented technology for product development. *Applied Ergonomics*, 33, 289-294.
- [18] Ramachandran, V.S. (2003). Reith Lectures on *The Emerging Mind: The artful brain*. Available at <http://www.bbc.co.uk/radio4/reith2003/lecture3.shtml> [Accessed 21 June 2010].
- [19] MacLean, P.D. (1949). Psychomatic disease and the “visceral brain”: Recent developments bearing on the Papez theory of emotion. *Psychomatic Medicine*, 11, 338-353.
- [20] You, H.C. & Chen, K. (2007). Applications of affordance and semantics in product design. *Design Studies*, 28, 23-38.
- [21] Hofstede, G. (2001). *Cultures Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations across nations*. (2nd ed.) Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA, USA.
- [22] Forty, A. (2000). *Objects of desire: Design and Society since 1750*. Thames & Hudson, Inc., New York, NY, USA.
- [23] Gajendar, U. (2008). Experiential aesthetics: A framework for beautiful experience. *Interactions*, 16, 6-10.
- [24] Locher, P., Overbeeke, K., & Wensveen, S. (2010). Aesthetic interaction: A framework. *Design Issues*, 26, 70-79.
- [25] Richards, S. (2005) *TETRA Radio: Design research and industrial design*. Design Integration, Motorola, Plantation, FL, USA.